

THE ESSENCE OF CONSCIOUSNESS AND ITS GENESIS

Karimov Bozarkul Khudaiberdiyevich

Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology, associate professor of the "Social Sciences" department, candidate of philosophy

Annotation: *The article describes the origin of mind, its multiversity and complexity, explains multilateral i.e. ontological, gynecological, social, pedagogical and psychological approaches that are necessary' to understand the essence of mind. Also the article enlightens the harmony of mind with spirit, first of all with the forms of sense, intellect, imagination, thinking as well as physiological and psychoanalysis principles.*

Key words: *Consciousness, reflection, conditional and non-conditional reflections, a human brain, language and thinking, the using (manipulation) of consciousness in anti-humanistic or countervailing purposes.*

The humanity today or tomorrow will definitely ask the question what is the purpose of its existence. This is not a simple question and to find the answer the humanity will have to look back to the history. The life of humanity is not short it is measured by the age of the Earth. The Earth and the Sun spent 4.5 billion years for the intellect to appear. This is not a short period. We are the product of a long-term natural process. It is obvious that our mind appeared as a weapon in the struggle for survival. And this exceptionally manifested mind's property which is the ability of matter, the universe to feel itself, the ability of nature to sense itself. This is really a miracle, a phenomenon - a singular case. We can come across with different big or small miracles in life.

Actually, do we understand the essence of our mind? How do we use the capabilities of our mind and intelligence? What are the mysterious, astonishing sides of mind and insanity? The intelligence is the highest form of a mental activity, it is the process of reflection of objective reality in mind. The intelligence is a weapon to understand the environment, social activities, reality as well as a fundamental prerequisite for human activities, Creative works, discoveries, inventions, suggestions are the products of the intelligence.

The role of mind and intelligence is very important in the development of society. In addition, the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in his book "The highest spirituality is an unbeatable power" noted for a reason that if we compare, the,

implementation of dreams inherent to human being, the required matter and spiritual factors for his intellectual existing, to wings of a bird, I think it would be reasonable.” Due to a multiversity and complexity of mind, it is studied by many subjects and that’s why the mind is a spiritual phenomenon that cannot be described generally. The mind is only inherent for a human being that summarizes the reflection of reality by the help of speech and tongue, according to the purpose, the subjective form of the objective world that is manifested constructively und creatively.

From the first years of independence human being and his life is being ascended as a superior value. In particular, studying of different sides of spiritual world of human being is becoming the actual problem nowadays. The base of this problem is connected with the subject - human mind and spirit.

These problems were scientifically justified by I. P. Pavlov and I. M. Sechenov in their teachings about physiological principles of mind. I. P. Pavlov noted that habitual harmony in mind and spirit problems should not be limited only to the conditional and unconditional reflexes. In point of fact later Sigmund Freud has justified relationships of a mind and insanity in his works.

Sigmund Freud noted that: “There are unperceived primitive instincts hidden in us and no any culture can protect person from their sudden manifestation; the instincts that are inherent primitive periods, that are far from ethical concepts lay in insanity. No matter how much we try to get rid of these primitive instincts we cannot escape from them completely, at least we can forward them to create cultural and ethical concepts.”

The human brain plays an important role in emerging and developing of mind. Brain is a central part of human and animal nervous system; brain ensures the control of complex vital functions and environment interactions of organism. Human brain weights 1000-1400 g and consists of 14-15 billion nerve cells. If it was possible to model the nerve endings then it would be possible to make a cybernetical device equivalent to the building of Moscow State University. In the book of Roger Penrose “The Road to Reality: A Complete Guide to the Laws of the Universe” it is stated that the process of perception has a materialistic nature there are mind carriers under the brainstem. According to him these are microtubules contained in neurons. Up to now they are considered as a transport units inside the cell canals. As per the new theory the information is collected and processed not by neurons but by microtubules. Of course, this is only a theory and it is difficult to prove it in practice. Because there is another factor, subjection of material to spirit, passing to possession of mind is the process which cannot be explained reasonably. Modern scientists including Penrose are studying the organ which acts as a “mediator” between the mind and matter that emerges the action. Even though it seems strange to study this small organ which is

conditionally called as “microtubules” this study has just started. From the very beginning the subject has faced with complex situations. As studying the universe, the space requires a lot of calculations, studying the “mind carriers”, identifying their moving factors will require so much efforts. Thus, the chain of events is as follows: scientists have discovered the first agent to influence the matter (the human mind) of the brain and call it neurons. After a while by the help of nanotechnologies it was found that neurons are not the last point, there are tubes called “mind carriers” in between. The interesting point is that the essence of these tubes is not determined, according to the scientists there may be found other binders of mind will to the body. The point here is not in which organ performs what function but what kind of algorithm the reality is based on. The scientists are trying to find the algorithm of this process.

In order to enlighten the problem of mind modeling process Penrose has covered a wide range of events and scientific knowledge: algorithm of mathematical mind, Turing modeling machines, theory of complexity, Godel’s theorem, the issue of matter teleportation, paradoxes of quantum physics, entropy events, the issue of origin (formation) of world (space, universe), black holes, the structure of human brain and others. Therefore his books are interesting for the specialists of humanitarian and natural sciences as well as wide range of booklovers. On this issue, Penrose summarizes, “I think that I cannot interpret mind in the context of modern theoretical physics”, and suggests that artificial intelligence should not and need not be created. According to scientists, human beings use a tenth of their brain capacity. If a person uses half of the available resources, he will be able to study 40 foreign languages, pass the exam for 40 higher education institutions, finish excellent grades, and memorize a great 15-volume book. Scientists still cannot explain why we cannot use this opportunity.

The American mathematical scientist, Von Neuman, the author of the computer-based structure, calculated the amount of information that can be stored in the human brain. In his opinion, the human brain can remember a great deal of information. Even so, that huge amount of information does not even exist in the world’s largest libraries. Unfortunately, the brain has the ability to remember randomly. The information contained therein is different. But the brain works slower with information that we encounter in our everyday life. Perhaps during human evolution, human memory will grow, and our future generations will be able to remember a whole book or many numbers. Until now, people with such capabilities are rarely found and are accustomed to calling them phenomena. The owners of the unique memory existed in all epochs. We know from the history that Julius Caesar and Alexander Zulkarnain remembered the name of each soldier in the 30,000-strong army. The same is true with Cyrus the king

of Persia. Well-mathematical scientist Leonard Euler amazed everybody with his ability to remember numbers. He calculated the results of the sixth level of all the numbers up to 100 without error. The Academic Chaplign would have been able to call the wrong phone number which he rang five years ago without any errors. The Great Russian chess player Alyokhin scored blindly with 30-40 opponents.

In conclusion, their purpose is that they try to lead them to a meaningless life by misleading the minds of tins people. At the same time, they try to instill the ideology they want into people by subordinating them to themselves.

List of Used Literature.

1. Санджар, М. Одним из факторов чистоты сердца является Футуват. *Международный журнал инноваций в инженерных исследованиях и технологиях*, 98-101.

2. МУРАДОВ, С. А. СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКИЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ ФАРИДУДДИНА АТТОРА. *МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО "Издательство Молодой ученый"*, (51), 529-531.

3. Мурадов, С. А., & кизи Касимова, Ф. Ф. (2022, December). ФИЛОСОФИЯ ДИЗАЙНА: ОСОБЕННОСТИ И СУЩНОСТЬ. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*. (Vol. 1, No. 7, pp. 51-59).

4. Санжар, М. (2020). Взгляды Фаридуддина Аттара на бытие. *Международный журнал прикладных исследований. ИДЖАР*, 6(6), 34-36.

5. Муродов, С. А. (2009). Ибн Сино, Аттор ва Навоий асарларида кушлар тимсоли. *Имом ал-Бухорий сабоқлари», Маънавий-маърифий, илмий-адабий журнал. Тошкент*, 273-276.

6. Мурадов, С. А. Современные методы философии и их значение в развитии мышления человека. *Актуальные исследования*, 51.

7. Murodov, S. A. (2022, November). Relationship between the universe and man in the works of Fariduddin Attor. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*. (Vol. 1, No. 6, pp. 35-41).

8. Karimov, B. K. (2022). HARMONY OF MIND AND SPIRIT. *THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD*, 1(2), 56-61.

9. Каримов, Б. (2011). Гармонизация взаимоотношений государства, общества и человека как основа справедливого общества. постановка вопроса. *Fuqarolik jamiyati. Гражданское общество*, 8(1), 71-73.

10. Мирзакулов, Б. Т. (2015). Дипломатические и торговые связи Бухары с Россией XVI–XVIII вв. *Молодой учёный*, 20, 548.

11. Мирзакулов, Б. Т. (1994). Рабочая кооперация Узбекистана в 20-е-начале 30-х гг.

12. Султонова, Л. С. (2022). МЕСТО ИНЖЕНЕРНОЙ ПЕДАГОГИКИ В ПОДГОТОВКЕ БУДУЩИХ ИНЖЕНЕРОВ. *YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS*, 1(6), 29-34.
13. Sultanova, L. (2021). The historical roots of spiritual education of youth. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 461-463.
14. Aminovna, B. G. (2021). The role of social system and political ideas in achieving human prosperity. *Thematics Journal of Education*, 6(November).
15. Аминовна, Б.Г. (2022). ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ВНУТРЕННИХ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ ПУТЕЙ СВЯЗИ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОАЗИАТСКИХ КОРОЛЕВСТВ В РАЗВИТИИ ТОРГОВЛИ. *Web of Scientist: Международный научный исследовательский журнал*, 3 (10), 12:00–12:05.
16. Темиров, Ш. Т., & Азимов, А. А. (2016). Экономический и культурный рост народов центральной азии в IX-X веках. In *Интеграция современных научных исследований в развитие общества* (pp. 104-105).
17. Jahongir, S. (2020). Philosophical views of Umar life. *Academicia. An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal.–India*, 10(4), 360-364.
18. Shodiev, J. J. (2020). Interpretation of moral facts in the opinions of Umar Khayyam. *International engineering journal for research & development.-India*, 5(3), 143-148.
19. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. Interpretation of the image of may in the ruba of Umar Khayyam. *Monografia pokonferencyjna science, research, development*, 33, 2020-30.
20. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайём фалсафий қарашларида инсон тақдири ва эркин ирода масаласи. *Наманган давлат университети Илмий ахборотномаси*, 2, 197-204.
21. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайёмнинг асосий асарлари ва рубойларининг тузилиши, мазмуни ва таҳлили. *Илм Сарчаишмалари.-Урганч*, 10, 44-47.
22. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайём рубойларининг талқин ва тавсифи. *Наманган давлат университети Илмий ахборотномаси*, 9, 206-210.
23. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайёмнинг ижтимоий-ахлоқий қарашлари. *Фалсафа ва ҳуқуқ.–Тошкент*, 3, 107-110.
24. Shodiev, J. (2021). The problem of knowledge in the philosophical views of Umar Khayyam. *Imam al-Bukhari IBS Journal*, 2.
25. Шодиев, Ж. (2022). Илк уйғониш даврида–комил инсонни шакллантириш ватарбиялашда тасаввуф таълимотининг ўрни. *Scientific Bulletin of NamSU-Научный вестник НамГУ-NamDU ilmiy axborotnomasi–2022-yil_4-сон*, 229.
26. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. Мамлакатимизда инсон қадрини юксалтиришнинг ижтимоий-фалсафий масалалари. *Қарду хабарлари. Илмий-назарий, услубий журнал. Махсус сон (Ижтимоий фанлар)*.
27. Shodiev, J. J. (2020). INTERPRETATION AND DESCRIPTION OF UMAR KHAYYAM RUBAYA. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 2(9), 206-211.

28. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2022). AGAINST IGNORANCE-FIGHTING WITH ENLIGHTENMENT THE MAIN CRITERIA IN IMPROVING HUMAN VALUE. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(10), 1160-1164.
29. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2022). ATTITUDE TO HUMAN DIGNITY IN THE PERIOD OF AMIR TEMUR AND TEMURIDS DYNASTY. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(5), 43-47.
30. Shodiyev, J. (2021). JAMIYATDAGI MEHNAT MUNOSABATLARI SHAROITIDA MA'NAVIY SALOHİYAT. *Журнал истории и общества*, (2)
31. SHODIEV, J. (2021). SOCIO-POLITICAL LIFE AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE IN THE PERIOD OF UMAR KHAYAM. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz)*, 1(1).
32. Shodiyev, J. (2021). O'ZBEKISTONDA IJTIMOİY-SIYOSIY KOMMUNIKATSIYA RIVOJLANISHIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SIYOSATI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(2), 409-416.
33. Shodiyev, J. J. (2020). U THE QUESTION OF HUMAN DESTINY AND FREE IN THE PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS OF OMAR KHAYYAM. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 2(2), 197-202.
34. Shodiev Jahongir Jurakulovich. Interpretation of moral facts in the opinions of Umar Khayyam. *International Engineering Journal For Research & Development* 2020/4/16.
35. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2023). The role of the national idea in increase of human values. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(10), 1160-1164.
36. Shodiyev Jahongir Jo'raqulovich. Inson qadri va uning huquqlari eng oliy qadriyat: tarixiy-huquqiy meros. *Ilm sarchashmalari/ Urganch – 3.2023*. 19-21.
37. Azimov, A. A., & Avliyokulov, U. M. (2019). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭСТЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ ЭПОХИ АБУ АБДУЛЛАХ РУДАКИ. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 560-562.
38. Азимов, А. А., & Темиров, Ш. Т. (2016). Политическая и социальная жизнь в бухарском эмирате во взглядах ахмада дониша. In *Интеграция современных научных исследований в развитие общества* (pp. 66-67).
39. Азимов, А. А., & ўғли Рўзиев, А. Ш. (2022, December). ОСОБЕННОСТИ КНИГИ АВЕСТА. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*. (Vol. 1, No. 7, pp. 37-42).
40. Azimov, A. A. (2022). PHILOSOPHICAL AND ETHICAL IDEAS OF THE EARLY RENAISSANCE OF THE EAST IN CENTRAL ASIA AND THEIR REFLECTION IN THE VIEWS OF ZAKARIA AR RAZI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(7), 57-62.
41. Азимов, А. А., & Темиров, Ш. Т. (2016). КУЛЬТУРНАЯ И АРХИТЕКТУРНАЯ ВЗАИМОВЛИЯНИЯ ВОСТОКА И ВОСТОЧНОЙ ЕВРОПЫ С БУХАРОЙ. In *Современные тенденции развития науки и производства* (pp. 33-34).

42. Bafoev, F. M. (2020). О НЕКОТОРЫХ КОНТУРАХ НОВОГО МИРОВОГО ПОРЯДКА: ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ, ПРОГНОЗЫ, ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (12), 388-390.
43. Бафоев, Ф., Мирзаходжаев, А., & Мирзаев, А. (2018). Принцип неделимости безопасности: непрерывность, целостность, универсальность. *Fuqarolik jamiyati. Гражданское общество*, 15(1), 80-83.
44. Феруз, Б. (2015). Среднесрочные приоритеты США в Центральной Азии: основы, стимулы, коррективы. *Центральная Азия и Кавказ*, 18(2), 27-37.
45. Бафоев, Ф. М. (2022, November). СТАТИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ДАННЫЕ КАК ИНДИКАТОР ЭФФЕКТИВНОЙ РЕАЛИЗАЦИИ ЦЕЛЕЙ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ (ЦУР). In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*. (Vol. 1, No. 6, pp. 42-50).
46. Бафоев, Ф. (2012). К ВОПРОСУ ОБ ЭВОЛЮЦИОННОМ ПРИНЦИПЕ СТРОИТЕЛЬСТВА НОВОГО ОБЩЕСТВА В НЕЗАВИСИМОМ УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Fuqarolik jamiyati. Гражданское общество*, 9(1), 54-55.
47. Bafoev, F. (2019). LIBERAL ISLAM IN THE CONTEMPORARY WORLD: NEW LANDMARKS OF TRUMP'S ADMINISTRATION. *Central Asia & the Caucasus (14046091)*, 20(2).
48. Бафоев, Ф., Мирзаходжаев, А., & Мирзаев, А. (2018). Принцип неделимости безопасности: непрерывность, целостность, универсальность. *Fuqarolik jamiyati. Гражданское общество*, 15(1), 80-83.
49. Феруз, Б. (2015). Среднесрочные приоритеты США в Центральной Азии: основы, стимулы, коррективы. *Центральная Азия и Кавказ*, 18(2), 27-37.
50. Шукуруллаев, Ю. (2022, December). СОЗДАНИЕ ВОЕННЫХ УСТАВНЫХ ГРУПП ЕВРОПЕЙСКОГО ТИПА В БУХАРСКОМ ЭМИРАТЕ. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE" THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS"* (Vol. 1, No. 4, pp. 42-51).
51. Шукриллаев, Ю. А. (2006). Бухоро амирлигида кўшин ва ғарбий иш (1756-1920 йиллар). Тарих фанлари номзоди илмий дражасини олиш учун езилган диссертация.-Тошкент, 2006.
52. Шукруллаев, Ю. А. Армия Бухарского эмирата и военное дело (1756-1920 гг.). Автореферат кандидатской диссертации по истории.-Ташкент, 2006.-26 с.; К вопросу о дипломатических сношениях между Россией и Бухарой через Оренбург в конце XVIII-начале XIX веков. *Общественные науки в Узбекистане*.-1962, 7, 55-59.
53. Ахмеджанов, М. М., & Нурматова, Н. У. (2017). Роль воспитания молодежи в духе толерантности в процессе глобализации. *Молодой ученый*, (7), 421-422.
54. Нурматова, Н. У. (2017). Применение мультимедийных технологий в образовательных учреждениях. *Міжнародний науковий журнал Інтернаука*, (6), 25-27.
55. Ахмеджанов, М. М., & Нурматова, Н. У. (2016). Farabi-first philosopher in his times. *Молодой ученый*, (2), 943-944.

56. ЗОИРОВ, Э. Х. НАУЧНОЕ НАСЛЕДИЕ МАХДУМИ АЪЗАМА. *АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ Учредители: ООО" Агентство перспективных научных исследований"*, (20), 29-32.

57. Зоиров, Э. Х. (2022, December). ДУХОВНОЕ НАСЛЕДИЕ МАХДУМИ АЪЗАМА. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION"* (Vol. 1, No. 4, pp. 121-131).

58. Zoirov, E. H. (2021). Questions of ontology of nature in the teachings of mahdumi azam. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(5), 91-94.

59. Зоиров, Э. Х. (2022). ОРИФ РЕВГАРИЙ-ВТОРОЙ ПИР БУХОРО-И-ШАРИФ. *YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS*, 1(6), 35-43.

60. Khalilovich, Z. E., & Orifovich, D. G. (2020). ANALYSIS OF THE TEACHINGS OF MAHDUMI AZAM AND CLASSIFICATION OF PAMPHLETS. *International Engineering Journal For Research & Development*, 5(4), 4-4.

61. Nigmatovna N. G., Erkinovna U. V. Pharaoh of the weavers of bahauddin naqshband // *Academicia: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*. – 2020. – Т. 10. – №. 5. – С. 922-926.

62. Наврўзова, Г. (2005). Нақшбандия тасаввуфий таълимоти ва баркамол инсон тарбияси. *Тошкент: "Фан"*, 233.

63. Nematovna, N. G. (2021, February). The essence of Abu Ali Sina's treatise on birds and the influence of mystical ideas on its development. In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 16, No. 1, pp. 19-23).

64. Наврўзова, Г. Н. (2021). Махдуми Аъзам Нақшбандия асоси бўлган тўрт калима хусусида. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(3), 188-199.

65. Наврўзова, Г. Н. (2007). Нақшбандия-камолот йўли. *Тошкент: "Фан"*, 189.